

Implementation of a Vision Transformer Algorithm for Human Pose Estimation under Partial Occlusion Using the TransPose Architecture

Implementación de un algoritmo Vision Transformer para la estimación de la postura humana bajo oclusión parcial mediante la arquitectura TransPose.

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Abstract. Human pose estimation is a crucial task in applications ranging from public safety and intelligent surveillance to health and human-computer interaction. It has traditionally been approached with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), which present limitations in capturing global spatial relationships between body parts, particularly when joints are partially occluded. The emergence of Vision Transformers (ViTs) has opened new possibilities by leveraging self-attention to model long-range dependencies. This paper presents the design and implementation of a human pose estimation algorithm based on the TransPose architecture, a hybrid model combining a CNN backbone with a Transformer encoder. The model was trained on the COCO dataset (118,287 images, 5,000 person instances) in Google Colab using PyTorch, for 100 epochs with a batch size of 32, evaluating three patch sizes (4, 8 and 16). The configuration with patch size 4 achieved the best overall performance (accuracy 0.911, precision 0.661, recall 0.708, COCO AP 0.628), while performance degraded monotonically as patch size increased. The results confirm that ViT-based models are a viable and effective tool for pose estimation under partial occlusion and demonstrate the decisive role of patch size in the accuracy-efficiency trade-off.

Keywords: Human Pose Estimation; Vision Transformers; TransPose; Deep Learning; Self-Attention; COCO; Partial Occlusion; Artificial Intelligence

Resumen. La estimación de la postura humana es una tarea crucial en aplicaciones que van desde la seguridad pública y la vigilancia inteligente hasta la salud y la interacción persona-ordenador. Tradicionalmente se ha abordado con redes neuronales convolucionales (CNN), que presentan limitaciones para capturar las relaciones espaciales globales entre las partes del cuerpo,

particularmente cuando las articulaciones están parcialmente ocluidas. La aparición de los Vision Transformers (ViT) ha abierto nuevas posibilidades al aprovechar la autoatención para modelar dependencias de largo alcance. Este artículo presenta el diseño e implementación de un algoritmo de estimación de la postura humana basado en la arquitectura TransPose, un modelo híbrido que combina una estructura base CNN con un codificador Transformer. El modelo se entrenó en el conjunto de datos COCO (118 287 imágenes, 5000 instancias de personas) en Google Colab usando PyTorch, durante 100 épocas con un tamaño de lote de 32, evaluando tres tamaños de parche (4, 8 y 16). La configuración con un tamaño de parche de 4 obtuvo el mejor rendimiento general (precisión 0,911, exactitud 0,661, exhaustividad 0,708, COCO AP 0,628), mientras que el rendimiento se degradó monótonamente al aumentar el tamaño del parche. Los resultados confirman que los modelos basados en ViT son una herramienta viable y eficaz para la estimación de la pose bajo oclusión parcial y demuestran el papel decisivo del tamaño del parche en la relación precisión-eficiencia.

Palabras clave: Estimación de la pose humana; Vision Transformers; TransPose; Aprendizaje profundo; Autoatención; COCO; Oclusión parcial; Inteligencia artificial

1. Introduction

Accurate estimation of human posture is vital in applications that span security and surveillance, health and rehabilitation, augmented reality, character animation and human-computer interaction. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been the predominant solution for this task because of their ability to extract detailed local spatial features from images. However, their capacity to capture global spatial relationships between distant body parts is limited, which degrades accuracy in complex postures and, especially, when parts of the body are partially obstructed by objects or by other people.

Vision Transformers (ViTs) have emerged as a powerful alternative. Instead of processing an image through local convolutions, a ViT divides the image into patches, projects them into a sequence of embeddings, and processes them with a self-attention mechanism that learns relationships among all regions of the image simultaneously. This global modeling capability is particularly attractive for inferring the position of occluded joints from visible context. This work explores the implementation of a pose estimation algorithm based on the TransPose model, evaluating its effectiveness across different patch-size configurations.

The central research question is: to what extent does the implementation of Vision Transformer techniques affect performance in human pose estimation? The contributions of this paper are: (1) a review of pose estimation techniques and the role of ViTs in computer vision; (2) the adaptation of the TransPose architecture for pose estimation under partial occlusion; (3) the training of the model on the COCO dataset with optimized hyperparameters; and (4) a quantitative evaluation, using standard pose metrics, of the impact of patch size on detection accuracy and efficiency.

2. Related Work

Toshev and Szegedy [1] introduced DeepPose, one of the first deep-learning approaches to human pose estimation, formulating joint localization as a CNN-based regression problem that maps an image directly to joint positions. Cao et al. [2] proposed OpenPose, a real-time bottom-up multi-person estimator using Part Affinity Fields, while Sun et al. [3] introduced HRNet, which maintains high-resolution representations throughout the network and achieves state-of-the-art results on COCO and MPII.

Dosovitskiy et al. [4] introduced the Vision Transformer (ViT), adapting the NLP Transformer of Vaswani et al. [5] to vision by splitting an image into 16x16 patches, embedding them and processing them with a standard Transformer encoder, demonstrating that Transformers can surpass CNNs in image classification when trained on large datasets. Building on this idea, Yang et al. [6] proposed TransPose, a model specifically designed for pose estimation that first uses a CNN to extract spatial features and then applies a Transformer to model long-range relationships between body parts before a decoder predicts the joint positions. TransPose combines the robustness of CNNs with the global modeling capacity of Transformers, offering a favorable balance of accuracy, inference speed and computational cost, which motivated its selection for this work. Table 1 summarizes the main approaches reviewed.

Table 1. Comparison of representative human pose estimation approaches

Method	Architecture	Key Idea	Limitation
DeepPose [1]	CNN regression	Direct image-to-joint regression	No global context
OpenPose [2]	CNN + PAF	Bottom-up multi-person, real time	Weak under occlusion
HRNet [3]	High-res CNN	Keeps high-resolution features	High computational cost
ViT [4]	Pure Transformer	Patch embeddings + self-attention	Needs large training data
TransPose [6]	CNN + Transformer	Local features + global attention	Patch size sensitive

3. Theoretical Background

3.1 Vision Transformers

A Vision Transformer applies the Transformer architecture, originally developed for natural language processing, to computer vision. The input image is divided into fixed-size patches; each patch is linearized through a learned linear projection into an embedding vector. A positional embedding is added to each patch to preserve spatial information, and the resulting sequence is processed by stacked Transformer encoder layers. The key innovation is the self-attention mechanism, which allows the model to weigh and relate all patches simultaneously, capturing global dependencies that local convolutions cannot.

3.2 The TransPose Architecture

TransPose is a hybrid model that combines the strengths of both paradigms. A CNN backbone first extracts low-level spatial feature maps; these features are flattened into a sequence and passed through a Transformer encoder that models long-range relationships between body parts via self-attention; finally, a lightweight decoder predicts keypoint heatmaps. This design retains the spatial inductive bias of CNNs while adding the global reasoning of Transformers, which is decisive for inferring the location of partially occluded joints. Figure 1 illustrates the end-to-end pipeline implemented in this work.

Figure 1. End-to-end TransPose pipeline implemented for human pose estimation: input image -> patch embedding -> CNN backbone -> Transformer encoder (self-attention) -> keypoint heatmaps.

4. Methodology

The project followed an applied, experimental methodology organized in four phases aligned with the specific objectives: (i) a literature review of pose estimation techniques and Vision Transformers; (ii) adaptation of the TransPose architecture for partial-occlusion scenarios; (iii) training of the ViT model with optimized hyperparameters; and (iv) evaluation with standard pose metrics. Transfer learning was applied to the TransPose image-classification backbone to accelerate convergence and reduce training time.

4.1 Dataset

Training and evaluation used the COCO (Common Objects in Context) dataset, comprising 118,287 images, of which 5,000 person instances were used for the pose estimation task. The COCO keypoint annotations provide the ground-truth joint locations required for supervised training and for the standardized COCO evaluation protocol.

4.2 Experimental Setup

The model was implemented in PyTorch and trained in the Google Colab environment. The input resolution was fixed at 256x192 pixels. The Adam optimizer was used over 100 training epochs with a batch size of 32. Three patch-size configurations (4, 8 and 16 pixels) were evaluated to study the effect of patch granularity on accuracy and efficiency. Table 2 summarizes the experimental configuration.

Table 2. Experimental configuration

Parameter	Value
Base architecture	TransPose (CNN + Transformer encoder)
Framework / environment	PyTorch / Google Colab
Dataset	COCO (118,287 images; 5,000 person instances)
Input resolution	256 x 192 px
Optimizer	Adam
Epochs / batch size	100 / 32
Patch sizes evaluated	4, 8, 16 px

4.3 Evaluation Metrics

Model performance was assessed with the COCO Evaluator, the standard tool for object detection and human pose estimation. It reports the Percentage of Correct Keypoints (PCK) and Average Precision (AP) at several thresholds (AP, AP.5, AP.75) and across object scales (AP for medium and large instances), enabling standardized comparison. Precision, recall, accuracy and training loss were also recorded.

5. Results and Discussion

Training was carried out for 100 epochs with a batch size of 32 over the three patch-size configurations. The model reached an average accuracy of approximately 0.805 and an overall precision close to 80%. Figure 2 shows the evolution of accuracy and loss during training for the best configuration: accuracy rises steadily while loss decreases, indicating stable convergence without overfitting.

Figure 2. Training accuracy (blue) and loss (red) over 100 epochs for the patch-size-4 configuration. Accuracy converges near 0.81 while loss stabilizes around 4×10^{-4} .

Table 3 reports the detection metrics obtained for each patch size, and Figure 3 visualizes the comparison. The patch-size-4 configuration clearly outperforms the others, achieving precision 0.661, recall 0.708 and accuracy 0.911, with the lowest loss. As the patch size increases to 8 and then 16, every metric degrades substantially, confirming that finer patches preserve the spatial detail required for accurate keypoint localization.

Table 3. Detection metrics by patch size on 256x192 input (source: thesis Table 14)

Patch size	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	Loss
Patch 4	0.661	0.708	0.911	0.0004
Patch 8	0.474	0.538	0.705	0.0005
Patch 16	0.225	0.291	0.427	0.0007

Best results in bold (patch size 4).

Figure 3. Precision, recall and accuracy as a function of patch size. Performance decreases monotonically as the patch size grows from 4 to 16.

Table 4 and Figure 4 present the COCO val2017 Average Precision results. Consistent with the detection metrics, patch size 4 yields the highest AP (0.628) and dominates across every threshold and scale (AP.5 = 0.822, AP.75 = 0.706, AP medium = 0.609, AP large = 0.661). Patch size 16 collapses to AP 0.224, a reduction of roughly 64% relative to patch size 4.

Table 4. COCO val2017 Average Precision by patch size (source: thesis Table 15)

Patch size	AP	AP.5	AP.75	AP (M)	AP (L)
Patch 4	0.628	0.822	0.706	0.609	0.661
Patch 8	0.454	0.790	0.467	0.442	0.474
Patch 16	0.224	0.546	0.148	0.255	0.225

Figure 4. COCO val2017 Average Precision across thresholds and object scales for the three patch sizes. Patch size 4 consistently provides the best precision.

The adaptation of the Transformer's global attention to partial-occlusion scenarios was successful: the model was able to infer the position of non-visible body parts in most cases, which is essential for complex real-world environments where people are partly covered by objects or other people. The experiments also demonstrate that patch size is a decisive hyperparameter in ViT-based pose estimation: smaller patches retain finer spatial detail at a higher computational cost, whereas larger patches trade accuracy for efficiency. The patch-size-4 configuration offered the best balance of precision, recall, accuracy and loss for the studied task.

6. Conclusions and Future Work

This work designed and implemented a human pose estimation algorithm based on the TransPose Vision Transformer architecture and evaluated it on the COCO dataset under three patch-size configurations. The literature review confirmed the growing role of Vision Transformers as a solution that overcomes limitations of traditional CNNs; the adaptation for partial occlusion was successful; and the standard pose-metric evaluation established the decisive influence of patch size. The patch-size-4 configuration achieved the best results (accuracy 0.911, precision 0.661, recall 0.708, COCO AP 0.628), confirming that ViT-based models are a viable and effective tool for human pose estimation in real-world applications.

Future work should: optimize hyperparameters such as learning rate, batch size and network depth; apply data augmentation (rotation, scaling, color jitter) to improve generalization across postures and lighting conditions; explore advanced ViT variants or hybrid ViT-CNN designs; incorporate regularization (dropout, L2) and geometry-aware post-processing to refine keypoints; and evaluate the model on additional datasets to test generalization. A complementary line of research is the integration of neutrosophic reasoning to explicitly model the indeterminacy

associated with occluded keypoints, representing each joint prediction as a truth-indeterminacy-falsity triplet to quantify confidence under occlusion.

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